

Synthesis of Hydrazones of 6-Hydroxy-3-Methyl-Coumarillic Acid Hydrazide as Antitubercular Compounds

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Isonicotinic acid hydrazide (Isoniazid) and its *N'*-isopropyl derivative (Marsalid) are effective drugs in the treatment of human tuberculosis. Although tuberculostatic activity has been shown by some other pyridine and non-pyridine hydrazides none is found superior to isonicotinic acid hydrazide. With a view to reduce toxicity due to free amino group, the condensation products of a number of hydrazides with various aldehydes and ketones were also examined.

Some naturally occurring oxygen heterocyclic compounds such as rotenone, khellin, usnic acid and karanjin, well known for their physiological activity, contain the furan ring system. It was therefore deemed desirable to investigate the hydrazones, containing a benzofuran ring system, for antitubercular activity. To this end, hydrazones obtained through the condensation of 6-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarillic acid hydrazide with a number of aldehydes and ketones have been synthesised. The hydrazide was obtained by the action of hydrazine hydrate on ethyl 6-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarone-2-carboxylate. The latter was obtained by condensing resorcinol with ethyl α -chloroacetoacetate in the presence of sodium ethoxide¹. Hydrazones were obtained in the usual way.

A number of carbonyl compounds used, contain hydroxyl group in ortho position. The possibility of a chelate ring formation by hydrogen bonding between the hydroxyl group and the terminal nitrogen atom of the hydrazone may make a significant contribution to the activity.

EXPERIMENTAL

Melting points are uncorrected

6-Hydroxy-3-methylcoumarillic acid hydrazide: To ethyl 6-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarone-2-carboxylate (9 g) dissolved in absolute alcohol (100 ml.), 99% hydrazine hydrate (10 ml) was added and the mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 4 hrs. Alcohol and excess of hydrazine hydrate was removed under reduced pressure. Crystallized from alcohol. Yield 70%, m.p. 250°.

Anal. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{10}N_2O_3$: C, 58.25; H, 4.85; N, 13.59, Found: C, 58.40; H, 5.00; N, 13.42.

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1. Hantzsch, *Ber.*, 1886, 19, 1290.

Hydrazones (Table I)

TABLE I

R	X	Yield (%)	Melting Point (°c)	Formula	Analysis (%)					
					Calc.			Found		
					C	H	N	C	H	N
Phenyl	H	74	235	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₃	69.30	4.76	9.52	69.50	4.80	9.40
4-methoxyphenyl	H	76	240	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄	66.66	4.93	8.63	66.80	4.75	8.70
2-hydroxyphenyl	H	73	228-230	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄	65.80	4.51	9.03	65.95	4.70	9.33
2-hydroxyphenyl	CH ₃	70	255	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄	66.66	4.93	8.63	66.80	4.65	8.80
4-hydroxyphenyl	CH ₃	70	235	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄	66.66	4.93	8.63	66.50	4.70	8.83
2-hydroxy-3-methyl-phenyl	CH ₃	75	250	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₄	67.45	5.32	8.28	67.60	5.50	8.40
2-hydroxy-5-methyl-phenyl	CH ₃	80	240	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₄	67.45	5.32	8.28	67.65	5.53	8.42
4-hydroxy-5-methyl-phenyl	CH ₃	82	245	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₄	67.45	5.32	8.28	67.40	5.30	8.33
2-hydroxy-5-chloro-phenyl	CH ₃	75	295	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	60.25	4.18	7.81	60.20	4.28	7.91
2,4-dihydroxyphenyl	CH ₃	85	240	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₅	63.52	4.70	8.23	63.42	4.90	8.08
2,4-dihydroxy-5-bromo-phenyl	CH ₃	86	235	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₅ Br	51.55	3.57	6.73	51.40	3.77	6.83
2-Hydroxy-4-methoxy-5-bromophenyl	CH ₃	82	275	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₅ Br	52.65	3.92	6.46	52.50	3.71	6.30
2-Hydroxy-4,6-dimethyl-5-chlorophenyl	CH ₃	80	250	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	62.95	4.91	7.24	62.72	5.10	7.34

An alcoholic solution of equimolecular quantities of aldehyde or ketone, 6-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarillic acid hydrazone and a few drops of sulphuric acid were refluxed on a water bath for 2 hrs. The reaction mixture was cooled and the solid was filtered, washed with alcohol and crystallized from alcohol-acetic acid.

The antitubercular activity of these compounds will be reported elsewhere.

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